

Synthesis of New 10-Substituted Phenothiazine Derivatives

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N-Acetylphenothiazine has been condensed with a number of aromatic aldehydes. The product of condensation reacted easily with hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine giving pyrazolines.

It is well known that the carbonyl group in 10-acetylphenothiazine **1** is very reactive and undergoes² the characteristic reactions with Grignard reagents, giving the corresponding hydroxy derivatives. The reactivity of the carbonyl group in **1**, has led us to extend this work on the reactivity of the acetyl group in the condensation reaction with aromatic aldehydes to cover other classes of 10-acetylphenothiazine derivatives. Thus, **1** was reacted with aromatic aldehydes **2** in ethanol in presence of 2% NaOH solution as a catalyst to afford **3** in yields ranging from 65-80%. Furthermore, compounds **3a-g** were prepared by an alternative route in which substituted cinnamoyl chlorides were condensed with phenothiazine in dry benzene in the presence of triethylamine as a catalyst.

Hydrazine hydrate itself, interacted with **3a-g** in alcohol gave an unstable pyrazolines, but when this was treated with glacial acetic acid or when the reaction itself was carried out in presence of glacial acetic acid, the stable N-monoacetylpyrazolines **4a-g** were obtained.

The structure of compounds **4a-g** has been established from their correct analytical data (cf. Table 2). The IR spectra of compounds **4a-g** showed absorption bands at 1687-1613 cm^{-1} (C=N) and at 1250-1227 cm^{-1} (C-N)³ and the absence of the N-H stretching frequency.

Phenylhydrazine reacted with **3a-g** in ethanol in presence of piperidine giving N-phenylpyrazolines **5a-g**.

3	R
a	C_6H_5-
b	<i>o</i> - OHC_6H_4-
c	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4-$
d	<i>p</i> -(CH_3) ₂ NC_6H_4-
e	2-furfuryl
f	<i>m</i> - $\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$
g	ferrocenyl ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{F} \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_4-$)

Fig. 1.

The IR spectra of compounds **3a-g** showed absorption bands at 1700-1696 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1608-1606 cm^{-1} (C=C)³.

The additive property of the exocyclic C=C in **3** conjugated with the carbonyl group prompted us to investigate their behaviour towards the action of hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Interaction of **3a-g** with hydrazine under suitable conditions gave a variety of pyrazolines.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 2

The structure of these compounds (**5a-g**) was established from their correct analytical data (cf. Table 3), and its IR spectra showed absorption bands at 1608-1592 cm^{-1} (C=N) and at 1242-1220 cm^{-1} (C-N). Also, compounds **5a-g** proved stable on boiling with acetic acid, mixing with concentrated sulphuric acid at room temperature or heating above its melting points which are the conditions that bring

out the cyclization of phenylhydrazones to pyrazolines. The pyrazolines gave the colour test characteristic for arylpyrazolines^{4,5}.

Also, when an ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution of 3a-g and hydroxylamine hydrochloride was refluxed, the isoxazoline derivatives 6a-g were obtained.

Fig. 4

The structure of compounds 6a-g has been established from their correct analytical data (cf. Table 4). The IR spectra showed absorption band at $1688-1612\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{N}$).

Experimental

All melting points were uncorrected. The IR absorption spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Unicam SP. 200 G infrared spectrophotometer.

Condensation of aromatic aldehydes with 10-acetylphenothiazine (3a-g): A mixture of 2g (0.01 mole) of 1 and 0.012 mole of the appropriate aldehyde in 50 ml. of ethanol and 1 ml. of 2% NaOH solution was refluxed for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in cold water. The precipitate was filtered off and recrystallized from ethanol as pale violet crystals.

Table 1 represents the physical and analytical data of compounds 3a-g.

N-substituted-10-N-acetylpyrazolinyphenothiazine derivatives (4a-g): (a) To a solution of 3a-g (0.01 mole) in ethanol 20 ml, hydrazine hydrate (50%, 4 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. Upon concentration an unstable yellow product separated out. On the addition of a few drops of glacial acetic acid to the ethanol solution of the crude product a crystalline yellow compound separated out which was crystallized from alcohol.

(b) The experiments were repeated using acetic acid (96%, 10 ml) as a solvent. The product, separated out on cooling, was crystallized from alcohol. They proved identical with N-monoacetyl derivatives prepared as described above.

Table 2, represents the physical and analytical data of compounds 4a-g.

TABLE-1 : 10-ARYL (FURFURYL OR FERROCENYL)-N-ACETYL PHENOTHIAZINE DERIVATIVES

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	M.F.	M.Wt.	Analysis (Calcd./Found)			
					C	H	N	S
3a	139-40	68	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{NOS}$	329	76.59 76.99	4.55 4.40	4.25 4.52	9.72 10.00
b	185-6 130-1	65	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$	345	73.04 73.23	4.34 4.52	4.05 4.21	9.27 9.52
		70	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$	359	73.53 73.88	4.73 4.52	3.89 4.01	8.91 9.04
d	155-6	75	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$	372	74.19 74.30	5.37 5.55	7.52 7.90	8.60 8.82
					e	148-9	77	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$
f	157-8	80	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$	374	67.38 67.53	3.74 4.01	7.48 7.62	8.55 8.66
					g	129-30	79	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{NOSFe}$

TABLE 2 : N-SUBSTITUTED-10-N-ACETYL PYRAZOLINYL-PHENOTHIAZINE DERIVATIVES

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	M.F.	M.Wt.	Analysis (Calcd./Found)			
					C	H	N	S
4a	188-90	75	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_8\text{OS}$	385	71.68 71.68	4.93 5.01	10.90 11.03	8.31 8.56
b	199-200	76	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}$	401	68.82 69.01	4.73 4.66	10.47 10.51	7.98 8.12
					c	159-60	80	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}$
d	216-7	66	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	428	70.09 70.34	5.60 5.88	13.08 13.32	7.47 7.38
					e	190-1	69	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}$
f	193-4	74	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	438	64.18 64.34	4.18 4.45	13.02 13.54	7.30 7.77
					g	201-2	60	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_8\text{OSFe}$

TABLE 3 : N-SUBSTITUTED-10-N-PHENYL PYROZOLINYL-PHENOTHIAZINE DERIVATIVES

Compound	M. P. °C	Yield %	M.F.	M.Wt.	Analysis (Calcd./Found)			
					C	H	N	S
5a	177-8	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ S	419	77.32	5.01	10.02	7.63
					77.45	5.34	10.22	7.91
b	201-2	68	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ OS	435	74.49	4.82	9.65	7.35
					74.51	4.99	9.51	7.05
c	186-7	65	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₃ OS	449	74.83	5.12	9.35	7.12
					75.00	5.13	9.55	7.51
d	145-6	77	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₃ S	462	75.32	5.62	12.12	6.92
					75.55	5.76	12.01	7.03
e	188-9	73	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	409	73.35	4.64	10.27	7.82
					73.55	4.87	10.51	8.01
f	210-11	60	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	464	69.82	4.31	12.07	6.89
					70.00	4.55	12.31	7.02
g	179-82 dec.	62	C ₃₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ SFe	526.5	70.72	4.75	7.98	6.08
					70.88	5.00	7.89	6.03

TABLE 4 : N-SUBSTITUTED-10-ISOXAZOLINYL-PHENOTHIAZINE DERIVATIVES

Compound	M. P. °C	Yield %	M.F.	M.Wt.	Analysis (Calcd./Found)			
					C	H	N	S
6a	173-4 dec.	40	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	344	73.25	4.65	8.13	9.30
					73.01	4.55	8.53	9.87
b	186-7 dec.	45	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	360	70.00	4.44	7.77	8.88
					69.99	4.54	7.56	8.63
c	168-9 dec.	50	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	374	70.54	4.81	7.49	8.55
					70.69	5.00	7.55	8.83
d	153-5 dec.	53	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	387	71.31	5.42	10.85	8.26
					71.54	5.56	10.98	8.15
e	199-200 dec.	48	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	334	68.26	4.19	8.38	9.58
					68.11	4.09	8.48	9.66
f	230-1 dec.	42	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	389	64.78	3.85	10.79	8.20
					64.88	4.00	11.01	8.42
g	230-1	40	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ OSFe	451.5	66.51	4.43	6.20	7.09
					66.33	4.32	6.52	7.18

N-Substituted-10-N-phenyl pyrazolinyl phenothiazine derivatives (5a-g): A solution of 3a-g (0.005 mole) and phenyl hydrazine (0.007 mole) in ethanol (80 ml.) and few drops of piperidine was refluxed for three hours. On concentration and cooling, crystalline product separated out. These were filtered and crystallized from ethanol as pale brown crystals.

Table 3 represents the physical and analytical data of compounds 5a-g.

N-Substituted-10-isoxazoliny phenothiazine derivatives (6a-g): A solution of equimolar quantities of 3a-g and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution was refluxed for 6 hr. On concentration and cooling the product was crystallized from alcohol.

Table 4 represents the physical and analytical data of compounds 6a g.

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